

Behaviour of Electrolytes in Mixed Solvents. Part VIII. Viscosity of Barium Chloride and Barium Bromide in Dioxane-water Mixtures

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The viscosities of barium chloride and barium bromide in dioxane-water mixtures at 10, 20, and 30% by weight of dioxane have been studied at 35°. The data fit well with the modified form of the Jones-Dole equation. The value of 'B' has been found to be dependent on the solvent composition and on the constituent ions.

The modified Jones-Dole equation,

$$\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = 1 + A\sqrt{c} + Bc^2,$$

suggested by us¹ has been found to apply in case of KCl, NaCl², MgCl³, and K₂SO₄⁴ in dioxane-water mixtures at 35°. The viscosity of BaCl₂ and BaBr₂ in 10, 20, and 30% dioxane-water mixtures has been measured at 35° to verify the applicability of the modified equation and also to examine the nature of the constant 'B'.

EXPERIMENTAL

BaCl₂ used was of B. D. H. 'AnalaR' quality whereas BaBr₂ was of 'E.P.'E. Merck variety. The estimation of Ba²⁺ content for both the samples was carried out by standard methods. The preparation of the solvents and solutions and measurements of viscosity and conductance were the same as reported earlier².

TABLE I

Solvent composition.	BaCl ₂			BaBr ₂			Δ B.
	A × 10 ² .	B.	z.	A × 10 ² .	B.	z.	
10%	2.25	0.230	1.00	1.13	0.284	0.90	0.054
20	2.31	0.405	0.98	1.22	0.440	0.95	0.035
30	2.41	0.648	1.04	1.31	0.675	0.95	0.027

TABLE II

Salts.	Conc. (moles/litre).	Observed viscosity.	Calculated viscosity by	
			J. D.	Modified J. D.
BaCl ₂	0.100	1.0003	1.0711	1.0667
	0.001	1.0012	1.0013	1.0013
BaBr ₂	0.100	1.0795	1.0721	1.0798
	0.001	1.0016	1.0011	1.0013

1. Patnaik and Das, *Curr. Sci.*, 1956, 25, 337.
2. Acharys, Das, and Patnaik, *this Journal*, 1957, 34, 56;
3. Das, *ibid.*, 1950, 36, 613.
4. Das, Das, and Patnaik, *ibid.*, 1960, 37, 683.

DISCUSSION

The change in viscosity with concentration for aqueous solutions of electrolytes is satisfactorily represented by the Jones-Dole equation¹. The evaluation of equivalent conductance (Λ_0) at zero concentration and calculation of 'A' by the Falkenhagen and Vernon expression have been reported earlier². The usual procedure to test the Jones-Dole equation has been applied and the equation has been found to hold good only for BaCl₂ in 10% dioxane solvent composition. For the other solvent compositions for BaCl₂ and BaBr₂, the Jones-Dole equation is inadequate and its modified form represents the experimental results satisfactorily.

The values of 'A', 'B', and 'z' for different solvent compositions calculated, as before¹, for both the electrolytes are recorded in Table I. The relative viscosities were next calculated by the use of these determined values of 'B' and 'z'. The calculated and the observed values are in good agreement for the range of concentrations of the solute, 0.100 to 0.001 *M* investigated at 10, 20, and 30% dioxane composition. Only two data for each of the electrolytes at 30% solvent composition have been recorded in Table II for illustration.

The data recorded in Table I show that with increase of the dioxane content in the solvent, the value of 'B' also increases which indicates that the value of 'B' is dependent on the composition of the solvent. The difference between the values of 'B', as shown in Table I, indicates that 'B' is not only affected by the composition of the solvent alone but also by the nature of the constituent ions, however small may be the contribution of the latter factor.